

Farming the Margins: Improving Agricultural List Frame Coverage

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Abstract

The United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) conducts hundreds of surveys annually and the Census of Agriculture (COA) every five years, compiling reports on nearly every aspect of U.S. agriculture, including food and fiber production, supply, prices, and farm labor. However, certain groups with historically lower participation in USDA programs may also experience lower list frame coverage, making data on these farms harder to obtain through traditional survey-based and administrative-data-based methods. Geographic and historical factors, along with networks and partnerships between farms and organizations, may lead to clustering of these underrepresented farms. This clustering suggests the potential efficiency of using targeted keyword searches based on specific regions, farm types, or topics (e.g., “urban farm,” “incubator farm,” “tribal enterprise”) to locate these farms. The current research focuses on identifying geographic regions with low USDA coverage, developing a new approach to find potential farms less likely to participate in USDA programs within these areas, and adding them to the list frame. Quantifying list frame coverage in these areas and characterizing the farms not included in the list frame are key objectives. By understanding the types of farms and regions identified, new list-building strategies can be developed and evaluated through case studies. This paper presents a case study and preliminary analyses aimed at improving list frame coverage for selected groups, potentially offering broader applications for enhanced agricultural data collection.

Key Words: Coverage, Web scraping, Farm Service Agency, List frame, Underrepresented populations, Agriculture

1. Introduction

The United States Department of Agriculture's (USDA's) National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) plays a pivotal role in quantifying the nation's agricultural production, conducting over 300 surveys annually and a Census of Agriculture every five years (years ending in 2 and 7). Most surveys conducted by NASS rely heavily on NASS's comprehensive list frame to identify and sample agricultural operations across the United States. This list frame is a meticulously maintained repository of all known farms and potential farms in the United States and its outlying regions, and it is crucial for producing efficient and accurate agricultural statistics. The NASS list frame includes a variety of types of farms and potential farms, including nurseries and ranches, which meet or potentially meet the definition of a farm, which is any operation with \$1,000 or more in sales or potential sales of agricultural products in a given year. The NASS list frame also includes agricultural operations that do not qualify as farms (e.g., out-of-business operations, landlord-only operations) and agribusinesses. NASS constantly updates and maintains the list frame, adding new records and deleting duplicates to maximize the quality of its surveys.

To build and maintain this list frame, NASS utilizes various sources of data. One of the sources is the Farm Service Agency (FSA), which serves as the main avenue through which the federal government provides credit to farmers via programs such as farm loans, conservation and resource management, and emergency relief. Given that the FSA attains detailed documentation of farm

operations when providing funding—covering aspects such as the type of farm operation, size of farm, crop yield, and livestock inventory—its records are invaluable for list-building and as a supplementary source of administrative data.

There are significant challenges to surveys when FSA administrative data are unavailable. The absence of FSA data can lead to increased uncertainty in survey results, potentially resulting from a less representative list frame and undercoverage of certain types of farms or regions. Undercoverage can lead to inaccurate estimates for crops, livestock, and other agricultural statistics. This issue is particularly pressing for operations that historically participate less in USDA programs and thus are often underrepresented in the list frame. For example, white male-operated farms remain the largest demographic segment of established and beginning farmers and the largest users of agricultural credit. Conversely, smaller farms, non-white farmers, and farms with lower sales values are less likely to be represented in the FSA data. This disparity may partly stem from the fact that socially disadvantaged farmers are more likely to engage in practices incompatible with the standardization necessary to participate in USDA programs and receive funding. A study examining credit usage within 20 states found that over 40% of socially disadvantaged ranchers and farmers did not participate in an USDA program (Ahrendsen et.al, 2022).

Given the significant portion of non-FSA farms potentially unaccounted for in the list frame, NASS needs to develop innovative methods outside of its historical processes to identify these non-FSA farms and gather data on how to contact them. One potential option is web scraping, a process that involves automatically extracting large amounts of data from websites and online databases. This technique allows for the gathering of a wide array of information that might not be accessible through traditional survey methods. Previous studies have found web scraping to be effective in generating list frames, particularly for identifying records that are underrepresented in traditional data sources. Barcaroli et al. (2016) demonstrated the utility of web scraping for collecting data on agritourism farms to enhance the Italian National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT) Farm Register. The study highlighted that web scraping could efficiently extract relevant information directly from farm websites, helping update and maintain the register with current data while reducing costs and respondent burden. This approach addresses challenges such as data quality and integration issues, proving beneficial for improving the accuracy and completeness of agricultural statistics.

While web scraping has emerged as a tool for building lists of specialized operations, including urban farms (Young et al., 2018) and hemp farms (Gerling et.al, 2024), careful research and planning are essential to ensure that searches for these types of operations use appropriate terminology to maximize the chances of finding relevant lists (Hyman et al., 2022; Young et al., 2018). Therefore, web scraping studies should describe the approach used to generate keywords (i.e., search term we use to narrow the search for lists of farms) and justify that approach. This paper discusses the preliminary investigation and exploratory methods NASS has employed to address these coverage gaps, including targeted web scraping and other innovative techniques, to enhance the completeness and accuracy of the list frame.

2.Methodology

2.1 Web Crawling and Web Scraping

Web crawling and web scraping are used to identify lists of farms that are historically underrepresented within the list frame. These include small livestock farms (e.g., goats, alpacas) and urban farms. However, it is possible that both farm types and lists of farms found might extend beyond small livestock farms and urban farms, because searchers are not restricted to searching specifically for these groups. The search is geographically limited to six states known to

have low Census of Agriculture coverage: Florida, California, Arizona, Maine, Washington, and Michigan (United States Department of Agriculture,2022)

2.2 Keyword Development

Search terms are developed based on geographic location, farm type, and organization type. For example, search terms like “list of urban agriculture in California” are used to locate relevant lists. The team then conducts keyword searches within the identified lists, focusing on organizations that fall into specific categories: association, community hub/network, blog/magazine/news, directory, government, tourism, non-profit, university/education, and goods and services. For the operational definitions of these organization types, see Appendix A.

Both keywords and lists are classified based on the primary farm commodity type, using NASS’s categories for farms. For keywords, this is accomplished by manually identifying words indicating the type of farm being searched for, e.g., “poultry farms” or “flower farms.” For lists, each list is investigated to try to determine the primary farm commodity type present on the list of farms. This is done using a combination of cues from the list organization (e.g., “Connecticut Sheep Association”), farm names (e.g., “Smith’s Sheep Farm”) and descriptions of products sold (e.g., “pasture-raised beef”). The commodity type that constitutes the majority of the farms on the list is used as that list’s commodity type. Where there is not a clear majority of one commodity type, or where descriptions of products sold indicate that many farms sell products of multiple different commodity types (e.g., fruit, vegetables and dairy), lists are classified as “multiple” commodity types. Where commodity types produced by farms cannot be determined based on names or descriptions of products sold, lists are classified as “unknown” commodity types. This category tends to include many lists of urban farms and community gardens, which are likely to be vegetable or fruit farms, but which can include other farm commodity types as well. These farm commodity types are ultimately collapsed into “crops,” “livestock,” or “none” for the purposes of analysis. Determining a primary farm commodity type of lists is generally straightforward if farm names include farm types or “products sold” descriptions are present. However, for this preliminary analysis, reliability testing on coding of list and keyword characteristics has not been completed. Geographic scale classification of the keyword search is based on the specificity of the geographic terms used. Keywords range from broad state-level searches (e.g., "urban farms in California") to more specific regional or city-level searches (e.g., "urban farms in Los Angeles"). Websites tend to explicitly mention the geographic scope of their operation lists, either in sections such as "About Us" or by the nature of the operations listed. For example, a directory focused on "Southern California" or "Bay Area" farms provides clear regional boundaries for classification. When the geographic scope is not explicitly stated, the team uses contextual clues from the listings themselves to infer the scale, such as grouping based on the proximity of listed farms to major urban centers or regions. This geographic classification helps ensure that searches are both comprehensive and relevant.

2.3 Data Extraction

Team members identify and scrape websites containing lists of farms. Lists are not scraped unless they contain five or more records and the website containing the list was updated in 2017 or later. Information such as the name of the operation, city, state, and zip code is extracted from these lists. R, Python, Google Sheets, Adobe Acrobat PDF tools, and manual copy and paste are all used as scraping tools. At minimum, both person or operation name and a zip code or city-state pair must be successfully scraped for probabilistic record linkage to be used.

2.4 Probabilistic Record Linkage

The extracted records are matched against the existing list frame using the probabilistic record linkage program AutoMatch (Broadbent and Iwig, 1999). Web-scraped data, including names, addresses, phone numbers, and emails, are standardized before matching to improve efficiency. Records on the list frame are classified as active records (currently involved in agriculture), criteria records (potential farms) and inactive records (out-of-business, deceased, or ineligible). The status for criteria records are confirmed through the National Agricultural Classification Survey (NACS)(USDA,2024). NASS prioritizes matching high-priority records first and runs three matches to deduplicate records. Potential matches are manually reviewed if uncertain. Records unmatched with valid addresses are added as criteria records (i.e., potential new farms); those without valid addresses are marked "undeliverable as addressed" (UAA) and researched further. An identification number for each web-scraped list is assigned to ensure traceability and to calculate metrics like the percentage of new criteria records.

2.5 Analysis of Trends

Data are evaluated using R Statistical Software (R Core Team 2021) with the tidyverse package (Wickham et al., 2019) and the stringr package (Wickham et al., 2019). The web-scraped list of records is loaded into R and each record is categorized based on whether, during record linkage, it is classified as a newly added criteria record (hereafter “potential new farm”) or a match with a record currently on the list frame (including active records, inactive records, and criteria records already on the list frame prior to record linkage). The stringr package is employed to succinctly classify list and keyword commodity types. Lists and keyword organization types are initially classified manually based on NASS’s categories for farms. However, if a web-scraped list is recorded as a list of primarily vegetable, fruit, grain, nursery, or hay farms, it is detected and reclassified as a list of crop farms. If a web-scraped list is recorded as a list of horse, cattle, sheep, aquaculture, poultry, or other animal farms, it is detected and reclassified as a list of livestock farms. Those with no specified commodity type are classified as ‘none’. Reclassification is conducted partly due to the small number of web-scraped lists initially available and to enhance the ability to identify trends. Similarly, for list and keyword organization type, string detection is used to identify which operations belonged to respective categories (e.g., directory and association) based on their initial manual categorical coding. Keyword and list geographic regions are categorized manually due to the specificity and uniqueness of each operation’s scope, i.e., county, city, region within state, state, regional (multi-state, but in a specific geographic region of the country), national, international. Counts (of all potential new farms) and their percentages (out of all web-scraped records within that category) for each variable categorization keyword and list are calculated and recorded.

3.Results

We focus on the 115 web-scraped lists from six study states, yielding a total of 4,965 records. Among these, 929 records, or 19% of all web-scraped lists, are classified as potential new farms.

Notable patterns are revealed by analyzing the trends in keyword searches. Searches conducted without specifying a crop or livestock farm type yield 78 lists and 3,493 records (Table 1). Of these records, 738 are identified as potential new farms, or 21% of all web-scraped records. Particularly, searches using livestock-related keywords are more successful in identifying potential new records (23%) compared to those using crop-related keywords (7%). This suggests that livestock farms may be underrepresented in current lists and highlights the potential of targeted keyword searches to fill this gap.

Table 1: Web Crawling Based on Keyword Commodity Type

Keyword Commodity Type	Lists Found with Keyword	Potential Farms	All Records	Potential Farms (%)
None	78	738	3,493	21%
Livestock	26	129	582	23%
Crops	11	60	890	7%
Total	115	929	4,965	19%

The type of organization referenced in the keyword searches also influences the number of new records identified. Searches including the keyword "directory" result in a higher overall number of records (Table 2). In contrast, searches using the keyword "association" lead to a slightly higher percentage (20%) of new records. A substantial portion of the lists found are provided by associations, highlighting their importance in list-building efforts.

Table 2: Web Crawling Based on Keyword Organization Type

Keyword Commodity Type	Lists Found with Keyword	Potential Farms	All Records	Potential Farms (%)
None	69	657	3,168	21%
Directory	42	254	1,707	15%
Association	4	18	90	20%
Total	115	929	4,965	19%

The geographic scope of the lists also plays a critical role. Nearly half of the lists are found by specifying a state (Table 3). These state-level searches result in one of the highest percentages of potential new farms (23%). The highest percentage of potential new farms is found when the county is specified during the keyword search (61%). However, this figure is inflated due to the small number of web-scraped lists within the category (n = 4). Lists focused on specific states tend to contain larger outliers or higher percentages of new farms, demonstrating the importance of targeted regional searches in improving list frame coverage. Of the 115 lists identified, 32, or nearly one-third, are provided by associations (Figure 1). Moreover, the majority of the lists identified contain operations within a specific state and exhibit larger outliers or higher percentages of potential new farms (Figure 2).

Table 3: Web Crawling Based on Keyword Geographic Scale

Keyword Commodity Type	Lists Found with Keyword	Potential Farms	All Records	Potential Farms (%)
None	26	110	627	18%
State	54	598	2612	23%
City	22	89	992	9%
Region within State	9	97	677	14%
County	4	35	57	61%
Total	115	929	4965	19%

Figure 1. Observed Number of Web-Scraped List Characteristics by Organization Type

Figure 2. Observed Number of Web-Scraped List Characteristics by Geographic Scale

4. Discussion

The investigation yielded informative findings, enhancing our understanding of gaps in the list frame and identifying strategies to address them. The study identified 929 potential new farms, which averages approximately 155 per state across the six study states. This study reveals critical insights that will guide future web-scraping efforts. Notably, it highlights the effectiveness of targeting livestock-related keywords and focusing on state or county-level searches, which have shown higher success rates in identifying new records.

Moving forward, the project will focus on several key areas to enhance the accuracy and comprehensiveness of the list frame used by NASS. Firstly, the study will aim to verify the farm status of the 929 new potential farms identified through web scraping and web crawling. This verification process is crucial to ensure that these identified operations meet the criteria for

inclusion as active farms on the list frame, thereby maintaining the integrity and reliability of the data.

Additionally, the plan is to assess the impact of these new records on survey estimates where possible, particularly at the county level and for specific domains. NASS disclosure review processes require certain minimum unweighted sample sizes in order for statistics to be published. Once these records are classified using NACS surveys and included in sampling programs and the Census of Agriculture, their contribution to minimum sample sizes can be studied directly. Additionally, current Census of Agriculture imputation methods use “donor” records with similar characteristics to farms with missing survey items (e.g., similar size, farm type, value of sales). Because records associated with this research project have identification numbers associated with specific lists linked to them, it would be possible to assess whether imputation using farms from the same list works better than picking a “donor” record with similar characteristics. This analysis will help us understand the extent to which the inclusion of these additional records contributes to more accurate and representative agricultural statistics.

Web scraping has played a role in multiple research efforts at NASS (Young et al. 2018, Hyman et al. 2022), but has only recently become a consistent part of list-building efforts. The success of this project, namely finding lists containing 929 potential new farms with a team of 12 volunteers (with about 4 focused on each of web crawling, web scraping, and project planning and data management), suggests that web scraping can serve as a powerful list-building tool at NASS. The scope of web scraping as a list-building tool can be expanded at NASS, using a plan outlining who will web crawl and scrape, which sorts of sites will be web scraped, how and how often they will be web scraped, and in which geographic areas scraping will be focused. Both existing analyses of list frame coverage and novel analyses developed for non-FSA farms specifically may be used to prioritize geographic areas for web scraping.

While web scraping presents an opportunity for list-building at NASS, it also presents possible challenges. First, not all websites allow web scraping, and scrapers may be blocked from accessing these websites’ data (Boeing and Waddell 2016). Web scraping may require manual editing of scraped records and creation of custom programs to scrape specific lists, both of which can be time-consuming. Natural language processing methods can provide some degree of automation. For instance, models can be trained to recognize specific fields such as name and address (Dumbacher and Diamond 2018), or algorithms can parse website structure and elements (Uzun 2020). There is also a concern that using web scraping to build NASS’ list frame would preclude the opportunity to create an independent, web-scraped frame for multiple-system estimation in the future. Concerns about independent frames can be circumvented if a multiple-system estimation model is used that allows for dependence among lists (e.g., Zwayne and van der Heijden 2005), and if sufficient record source and linkage data are retained to quantify overlap between the list frame at the time of record linkage and the outside source list or lists in question. Finally, the ultimate goal is to evaluate the classification methods used for keyword and list analysis. This includes assessing the reliability of current methods and exploring the application of advanced artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning techniques to improve classification accuracy. By leveraging these technologies, the expected outcome is to enhance our ability to identify and categorize farms accurately, thereby improving the overall quality of the NASS’s list frame.

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